

PREDICTION OF THE RESIN FILLET SIZE IN HONEYCOMB SANDWICH STRUCTURES BY CO-CURE PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

The resin fillet plays an important role in the bonding performances of co-cured honeycomb sandwich structures by hot pressing process. The numerical method based on resin flow-fiber compaction was developed to predict the resin fillet size under different processing conditions in this paper. The amount of adhesive weight for forming resin fillet was calculated respectively according to the decrease of the thickness of skins and the increase of fiber volume fraction. Processing parameters, including temperature and pressure cycle and the viscosity of matrix resin in prepreg were analyzed by the numerical method. The maximum error is less than 10% which shows that the predictions have a good agreement with the experimental results. The results also show that pressure factors influence the resin fillet size more significantly than temperature factors. This research provides a promising way to predict the forming quality of honeycomb sandwich structure composite and guidance for the optimization of process conditions and control of processing quality.

1 INTRODUCTION

Bonding strength of the panel and the core material is one of the important parameters for honeycomb sandwich structure, while the resin fillet is the decisive factor of the bonding strength. Studies have shown that the bonding strength of the honeycomb sandwich structure is greater as the resin fillet size is larger^[1-4]. Grimes^[5] discussed the role of the resin fillet in honeycomb sandwich structure. Increase the size of the resin fillet can improve shear strength and shear modulus of the panel and the stress in the resin fillet can be calculated by mathematical methods during plane tensile

test. Okada^[6] analyzed the resistant mechanism of resin fillet during fracture process and found that the absorption effect of fracture energy is better with the larger resin fillet. Rion^[7] found that the peeling failure occurs between the skin and sandwich during the roller peel test when the amount of adhesive film is little which equals the small resin fillet while the failure occurs in the honeycomb core when the amount of adhesive film is much which equals the large resin fillet. Julien^[8] developed an experimental method to calculate the resin fillet size for skin to honeycomb core bonding. However, it is hard to predict the resin fillet size in honeycomb sandwich structures by co-cure process. The numerical method based on resin flow-bed compaction was developed to predict the resin fillet size in this paper. The calculation data were compared with experimental results to prove its efficiency. Processing conditions were investigated to analyze the factors influence the resin fillet size.

2 THEORY AND IMPLEMENTATION

2.1 Materials

In this experiment, the Nomex honeycomb was produced by Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials (BIAM). Prepreg made of T300 carbon fiber plain weave fabric and moderate temperature curing epoxy resin also produced by Beijing Institute of Aeronautical Materials (BIAM) was adopted as the skin materials.

2.2 Theoretical Background

The basic assumptions in the model are: (1) the prepreg is idealized as a void-free fiber bed fully saturated with resin; (2) the resin is assumed to behave as an incompressible Newtonian fluid; (3) the body forces are neglected. At the same time, there is no lateral expansion due to the prepreg confined laterally in a rigid sheath. Besides, it is assumed that no resin can escape laterally or through the bottom while it is free to escape at the upper surface by applying the load through the very porous bleeders. With this approximation, the one-dimensional governing equations for flat-plate laminate, expressed in the Cartesian coordinates, can be written as:

2.2.1 Effective Stress Theory

The effective stress theory was introduced in soil mechanics to model the consolidation of soil by Terzaghi and Biot. Based on experimental data on compaction of fiber beds, Gutowski et al. applied this theory to the compaction of composites during cure. The effective stress formulation states that at any point in the laminate the stress is given by the expression,^[9]:

$$\sigma = P_f + P_r \quad (1)$$

2.2.2 Fiber Continuity

The individual fibers are assumed incompressible. We define a small deformable cubic element such that the volume of fibers it contains is always constant. Therefore, the fibrous bed continuity equation can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial \xi}{\partial z} = \frac{V_0(z,t)}{V_f(z,t)} \quad (2)$$

2.2.3 Resin Continuity

$$\frac{\partial \varepsilon}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial(\varepsilon v_z)}{\partial \xi} \quad (3)$$

2.2.4 Darcy's Law

In the deformed element, taking into account the variable thickness dimension (2), Darcy's law can be written as:

$$v_z = -\frac{K_z}{\mu} \frac{\partial P_r}{\partial \xi} \quad (4)$$

Now the preceding equations are combined to obtain the governing equation of the compaction model with the minimum number of dependent variables. In the fixed coordinate, the governing equation can be expressed as:

$$\frac{V_0^2}{V_f^2} \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{V_f \cdot K_z}{\mu} \frac{\partial P_f}{\partial V_f} \frac{\partial V_f}{\partial z} \right) \quad (5)$$

Or

$$\frac{V_0^2}{V_f^2} \frac{dV_f}{dP_f} \frac{\partial P_r}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{V_f \cdot K_z}{\mu} \frac{\partial P_r}{\partial z} \right) \quad (6)$$

In which Gutowski et al.^[10] fiber bed compaction model is adopted:

$$P_f = \frac{3\pi E}{\beta^4} \frac{\sqrt{\frac{V_f}{V_0}} - 1}{\left(\sqrt{\frac{V_a}{V_f}} - 1 \right)^4} \quad (7)$$

Equation (5) is severely non-linear due to the small change scope of the freedom V_f . On the other hand, V_f is a dimensionless variable: as for the two-dimensional flow problem, it is difficult to define the free flow boundary condition. We adopted the governing equation (6) to simulate the one-dimensional flow and compaction process. Although it is much more difficult to solve Equation (6) than Equation (5), it will make more sense to further study two-dimensional problems.

Equation (6) is transformed into the legible expression based on the mathematical theory:

$$\frac{V_0^2}{V_f^2} \frac{1}{dP_f/dV_f} \frac{\partial P_r}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\frac{V_f \cdot K_z}{\mu} \frac{\partial P_r}{\partial z} \right) \quad (8)$$

Where:

$$\frac{\partial P_f}{\partial V_f} = \frac{3\pi E}{\beta^4} \cdot \frac{\left((5/2) \sqrt{V_f/V_0} - 2 \right) V_f \sqrt{V_a} - (1/2) \sqrt{V_f/V_0} \cdot V_f^{3/2}}{\left(\sqrt{V_a} - \sqrt{V_f} \right)^5} \quad (9)$$

The flow-compaction Equation (8) is a complex non-linear transient different equation. In the solving process, the node coordinate is not changed, but the fiber volume fraction reflecting the fiber compaction alters with time. With the solution of Equation (8), resin flow velocity can be calculated during compaction. It is helpful to understand the intrinsic flow phenomena and study other physical phenomena further such as the effect of resin convective on the heat transfer.

To keep coordinate with Equation (8), Equation (4) should be transferred as:

$$v_z = -\frac{K_z}{\mu} \frac{V_f}{V_0} \frac{\partial P_r}{\partial z} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) is the final form to describe the resin flow in the fixed coordinate system. For boundary conditions, the initial and boundary conditions need to be specified to solve the transient

differential Equation (8), while Equation (10) needs no initial condition with free boundary condition, i.e., the boundary point is also solved by the governing equation. The state variable that describes the evolution of the flow-compaction process is the resin pressure P_r . Table 1 shows the initial and boundary conditions.

The initial fiber volume fraction of the composites, V_0 , is specified and the fiber bed is initially stress-free, so the initial resin is assumed to take on the applied pressure. A permeable boundary condition is specified by imposing a prescribed resin pressure at that boundary (i.e., ‘free flow’ boundary condition). The impermeability condition is equivalent to having a zero normal pressure gradient at the boundary^[11-14].

2.3 Simulation of resin amount

In the simulation, the honeycomb core is assumed to be bleeder material and the resin flows from the skin into the honeycomb under loads. The resin content decreases and the skin turn thinner since the resin flows out which can be used to calculate the amount of the resin. The geometric model is shown in the Fig. 1. The thickness of skin is 1.5mm and the thickness of the Nomex honeycomb is 15mm.

1Upper skin, 2Honeycomb core, 3Lower skin, 4Mould
 Fig. 1 The mesh and boundary conditions of the sandwich structure

The blue boundary means the move of the x axis is bounded to be 0, the move of the y axis is free and the resin pressure is free which is defined as force boundary. The yellow boundary means the move of the x axis is bounded to be 0, the move of the y axis is free and the resin pressure is bounded to be 0 which is defined as bleeding boundary. The green boundary means the move of the x axis is bounded to be 0, the move of the y axis is bounded to be 0 and the resin pressure is free which is defined as static boundary.

The process system was set as follows, the temperature increases from 298K to 393K at a rate of 2K/min and then holds for 2h, the pressure is applied at the beginning of heating-up and the pressure is 0.2MPa. The Fig. 2 shows the temperature and the resin viscosity of the skins.

The Fig. 3 shows the displacement of the upper surface of the skins during simulation. The upper surface of the lower skin descends 0.19mm and the upper surface of the upper skin descends 0.38mm which means both of the skins becomes thinner by 0.19mm. The amount of resin flows out can be calculate as:

$$M = \rho \times \Delta h \tag{11}$$

M means areal density of the resin for forming resin fillet in the formula, ρ means volume density

of the resin and Δh means the thickness variation of the skin.

Fig. 2 The temperature and the resin viscosity of the skins during process

Fig. 3 Displacement of the upper surface of the skins

The thickness variation of skins is actually equal though the resin viscosity of the skins is different during manufacturing. The skins stay pressed under forming pressure and then go through the process of low resin viscosity, when there is enough time for resin to flow out into bleeder materials, actually honeycomb. So the key factor is the compaction property of fibers and the resin viscosity difference between upper and lower skins does not affect the thickness variation significantly because of the same fiber compaction equation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The geometry model of resin fillet

The cross section of the resin fillet is shown in Fig. 4. The shape of resin fillet is uniform due to the same stress in the plane.

1 Honeycomb side wall, 2 Resin fillet, 3 Skin
Fig. 4 The cross section of the resin fillet

Fig. 5 The two-dimensional geometry model of resin fillet

The two-dimensional geometry model of resin fillet is set up as shown in Fig. 5. The model includes x axis, y axis and cross section of the resin fillet. θ_1 means the angle formed by resin fillet and honeycomb side wall and θ_2 means the angle formed by resin fillet and the skin. θ_1 and θ_2 are determined by interfacial force. According to Laplace equation:

$$\Delta P = \gamma_{lv} \left(\frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{1}{R_2} \right) \quad (12)$$

ΔP means the difference between liquid pressure and air pressure, γ_{lv} means gas-liquid surface tension, R_1 and R_2 respectively means the radius of curvature in cross section and the radius of curvature in cross section in vertical cross section. R_2 is infinite in the two-dimensional model, so the equation can be simplified as:

$$\Delta P = \frac{\gamma_{lv}}{R} \quad (13)$$

R is a constant to ignore the gravity force since ΔP is a constant. So the surface of the resin fillet is a circular arc and the radius of curvature is determined by θ_1 , θ_2 and the area of resin fillet. At the same time, the equation can be deduced. Fig. 6 shows the fore analysis of an infinitesimal arc.

Fig. 6 The fore analysis of an infinitesimal arc

According to the mechanical equilibrium, the following equation can be obtained:

$$\gamma_{lv} \sin(d\theta) \cong \gamma_{lv} d\theta \cong \Delta P dl \quad (14)$$

$$dl = \sqrt{dx^2 + dy^2} = dx \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{dy}{dx}\right)^2} = dx \sqrt{1 + y'(x)^2} \quad (15)$$

$$\theta = \arctan(y'(x)), \text{ so } \frac{d\theta}{dx} = \frac{y''(x)}{1 + y'(x)^2} \quad (16)$$

Then

$$\frac{d\theta}{dl} = \frac{d\theta}{dx} \frac{dx}{dl} = \frac{y''(x)}{(1 + y'(x)^2) \sqrt{1 + y'(x)^2}} = \frac{y''(x)}{(1 + y'(x)^2)^{3/2}} \quad (17)$$

$$y(x) = Y_c - \sqrt{R^2 - x^2 + 2xX_c - X_c^2} \quad (18)$$

((X_c, Y_c) is the center of curvature and R is the radius of curvature)

Finally

$$\frac{d\theta}{dl} = \frac{1}{R} \text{ and } \Delta P = \frac{\gamma_{lv}}{R} \quad (19)$$

3.2 Deduction and calculation

The height of resin fillet L_1 , the width of resin fillet L_2 and the area of resin fillet A can be indicated as follows:

$$L_1 = R \cos(\theta_2) - R \sin(\theta_1) \quad L_2 = R \cos(\theta_1) - R \sin(\theta_2) \quad (20)$$

$$A = \frac{L_2 R \cos(\theta_2) + L_1 R \cos(\theta_1) - R^2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_1 - \theta_2\right)}{2} \quad (21)$$

Taking account of the overlapping of resin fillet shown in Fig. 7, it is analyzed that the volume of resin fillet in every honeycomb cell can be calculated as follows:

$$V = 6 \left(\frac{dL_1 L_2}{4} - \frac{L_1 L_2^2 \tan(\pi/6)}{3} \right) \times \alpha \quad (22)$$

d is the circumscribed circle diameter of the honeycomb cell and α means the ratio between the cross section resin fillet area and the area of the right triangle made of L_1 and L_2 .

Fig. 7 Overlapping of resin fillet

$$\alpha = \frac{A1}{A1 + A2} = \frac{2A}{L_1 L_2} = \frac{L_2 R \cos(\theta_2) + L_1 R \cos(\theta_1) - R^2 (\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_1 - \theta_2)}{L_1 L_2} \quad (23)$$

For the hexagonal honeycomb cell, the area can be obtained by the equation:

$$s = \frac{3\sqrt{3}d^2}{8} \quad (24)$$

Then the average areal density of resin in every honeycomb can be calculated by the equation as follows:

$$M = \frac{\rho V}{s} = \alpha \left(\frac{4L_1 L_2}{\sqrt{3}d} - \frac{16L_1 L_2^2 \tan(\frac{\pi}{6})}{3\sqrt{3}d^2} \right) \rho \quad (25)$$

The average areal density of resin is the same one as the simulation result, so the resin fillet size can be calculated by the simultaneous equations made up by this equation (26) and equation (20).

$$\alpha \left(\frac{4L_1 L_2}{\sqrt{3}d} - \frac{16L_1 L_2^2 \tan(\frac{\pi}{6})}{3\sqrt{3}d^2} \right) = \Delta h \quad (26)$$

For example, the honeycomb sandwich structure with 1.5mm skins is set a rate of 2K/min from 298K to 398K and then holding for 2h and the initial pressure applied is 0.2MPa. The thickness variation Δh is 0.19mm. The θ_1 and θ_2 is measured to be 19.9° and 22.1°. The finally calculated results are that L_1 is 0.70mm and L_2 is 0.68mm.

3.3 Analysis of influencing factors for resin fillet size

All the processing parameters can affect the resin fillet size. The factors can be divided into two types, one is the factors can affect the contact angle between the resin and honeycomb side wall, the other is the factors can affect the resin amount to form resin fillet. The materials in this study were determinate which means the contact angle between the resin and honeycomb side wall is constant. So the time applied pressure and the pressure were selected to analyze their influences on resin fillet size.

To analyze the influence of time applied pressure, a set of different time applied pressure was selected with the same other processing parameters and the same pressure 0.2MPa. Similarly, a set of different pressures was selected with the same other processing parameters and the same time applied pressure 0s.

As shown in Fig. 8, the time applied pressure did not affect the resin fillet size until it was applied after 2850s and the phenomenon is almost the same on both the height of resin fillet L_1 and the width of resin fillet L_2 . The results were corresponding to the resin viscosity which was shown in Fig. 2, there is no significant difference of the resin fillet size between different times applied pressure as long as the resin viscosity is low enough to allow resin to follow out. The resin fillet size decreases when the time applied pressure is late.

As for pressure, the height of resin fillet L_1 and the width of resin fillet L_2 both increased with the improvement of forming pressure which was shown in Fig. 9. Since more resin was forced out with higher pressure, the growth arises obviously.

Fig. 8 The influence of time applied pressure on resin fillet size

Fig. 9 The influence of pressure on resin fillet size

Fig. 10 Comparison of the simulation results and experiment results

To prove its efficiency, the results calculated by this simulation method were compared with the experimental results with the same processing parameters. As shown in Fig.10, they have a good agreement since the maximum deviation is less than 10% which proves the reliability of this calculation method.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A numerical method on the basis of resin flow and fiber bed compression was developed to predict the resin fillet size under different processing conditions.

The amount of adhesive weight for forming resin fillet was calculated and the amount of adhesive was analyzed through mechanical equilibrium simultaneously.

The resin fillet size was then obtained according to simultaneous equations. The calculation results have a good agreement with the experimental results.

In summary, the calculation method provides a promising way to predict the forming quality of honeycomb sandwich structure composite and guidance for the optimization of process conditions and control of processing quality.

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